

D1.7 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessment - II

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Executive Summary

This document concludes the activities performed during WP1 regarding the collection of industrial requirements and the consequent definition of the most relevant metrics to be used for the assessment of the ShareWork system performances in industrial manufacturing environment. In this document, specific metrics are provided to allow the validation of the ShareWork system in each of the four use cases considered in the project. In addition to the metrics for the industrial impact evaluation, all technological modules of the ShareWork are here addressed, presenting the methodology, the baseline and the targets to validate the software modules performances with respect to the current state of the art. The information collected in this deliverable will be essential in WP7, when the system validation campaign and performance assessment will be performed.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>C2I</i>	<i>Command, Control and Intelligence</i>
<i>C4I</i>	<i>Command, Control, Communications, Computers and Intelligence</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>UAS</i>	<i>Unmanned Aerial System</i>
<i>UGV</i>	<i>Unmanned Ground Vehicle</i>
<i>CPCS</i>	<i>Central Process Control System</i>
<i>NPS</i>	<i>Navigation and Perception Sensors</i>
<i>PMS</i>	<i>Process Monitoring Sensors</i>
<i>RU-V1</i>	<i>Robotic Unit Version 1</i>

1 Introduction

This document proposes and analyse the most relevant metrics to be used for the assessment of the ShareWork system performances in industrial manufacturing environment. The work included in this Deliverable 1.7 moves from the basis of Deliverable 1.6, where KPIs for a general industrial scenario and for the ShareWork modules had been introduced. In this second iteration, specific metrics are provided to allow the validation of the ShareWork system in each of the four use cases considered in the project.

For the four use cases, iterative discussions with the industrial end users have occurred, in order to identify the most relevant requirements for their processes and identify a specific set of metrics that could best represent their need in terms of productivity, cost, safety and human-related factors.

In parallel with the definition of KPIs targeted to the industrial scenarios, all technological modules of the ShareWork are also investigated. Moving from the analysis performed in D1.6, each module is presented taking into account the situation in the industrial scenario before ShareWork implementation, the objectives and targets after ShareWork implementation and the methodology to validate the modules performances with respect to the state of the art.

Together D1.6 and D1.7 act as a basis for the System performance assessment and benchmarking activities that will be performed in task 7.4.

2 Structure and description of contents

D1.7 is divided into four main sections.

In the first section, the KPIs for the evaluation of the ShareWork system impact in the four industrial manufacturing process are identified and detailed. Starting from the general set of KPIs defined in D1.6, for each industrial scenario these KPIs are modified to meet the end users specific needs and requirements and a complete table is presented for each use case.

In the second section, performance metrics presented for each of the 14 technological modules of ShareWork. The general introductions provided in D1.6 are here updated reflecting the evolution of the work occurred in the last 6 months and, for each module, a set of metrics for their validation is presented. For each module it is presented how the defined metrics will be measured, what are the set targets and the starting baseline.

The final section provides the conclusions of the deliverable and the next steps of specific KPIs definition.

3 KPIs for industrial impact

In the first section of this deliverable, KPIs targeted to the evaluation of the performance of the ShareWork system in the four use cases are presented. In D1.6, a set of 16 main KPIs for industrial impact evaluation have been defined and have been considered as the basis to define the specific KPIs for each use case. The set of general KPIs defined in D1.6 was comprehensive of the main KPIs that are commonly used in manufacturing processes to assess performances, together with parameters that are more specific of human-robot collaborative systems and address the reception and acceptance of the robotic system by the human. The same approach has been followed for the definition of the specific KPIs presented in this document, in order to allow a complete description and evaluation of the four industrial scenarios targeted in the ShareWork project. The aim is, in fact, to evaluate the system performances with respect to the four main drivers of ShareWork, which are Productivity, Cost, Safety and Human Factor.

Table 1 shows the list of KPIs defined in D1.6, relating each one of them to the four ShareWork drivers.

Table 1 – KPIs correspondence to the four ShareWork drivers

KPI	Productivity	Cost	Safety	Human Factors
Utilization	X	X		
Efficiency	X			
Robot wait time	X			
Cycle time	X	X		
Performance	X			
Overall equipment effectiveness	X	X		
First time through	X	X		
Downtime	X	X		
Set up time	X	X		
Training hours		X		X
Unit cost		X		
Trust				X
Situation awareness			X	X
Workload	X			X
Reportable health & safety incidents			X	
Reportable environment incidents			X	

This list of KPIs has been used as a baseline to kick-off the definition of the specific metrics to evaluate the ShareWork system performances in the four industrial scenarios targeted in the project. Due to the inherent differences between the four scenarios, the final set of KPIs has

been defined following the end users' specific needs through iterative discussions and a cooperation process between the end users and their respective technical coaches. The result is a set of KPIs that is representative of each scenario specificity and target the end users' main needs and objectives.

While productivity, cost and Safety KPIs have been defined specifically for each use case scenario, human-factor KPIs are presented unified for all scenarios. This choice is due to the fact that the methodology for human-factor KPIs evaluation will be the same for all scenarios and is independent from the specific robotic system and from the task. Therefore, Trust, Situation awareness and Workload are presented in the next section and the methodology detailed for their evaluation is applicable to all industrial scenarios.

In the following sections, the specific scenarios addressed in the ShareWork project are briefly recalled through a step by step description of the human-robot collaborative task, to help the reader in the comprehension of the KPIs, and the KPIs defined for each industrial scenario are then presented. For each defined KPI, a description and a target are provided. When applicable, a baseline metric representative of the current situation is provided as well.

3.1 Human-factors KPIs

In D1.6, three metrics have been identified as KPIs for the evaluation of human-factors in human-robot collaborative industrial processes, namely Trust, Cognitive Load and Situational Awareness. Aiming at defining a comprehensive framework for the human factors in collaborative robotics, a detailed process of state-of-the-art review and analysis has been performed, to identify the most common and relevant practices applied in this field. A more detailed presentation of these findings is provided in D6.1. Below, the main details related to Trust, Cognitive Load and Situational Awareness are presented.

Trust

A standard definition of trust in the field of human factors comes from Sheridan¹, a pioneer in the study of trust in technology (1988, 2019). Sheridan defined a 7-item scale of trust, which is the most complete and widely used instrument in the field for both objective and subjective trust (1988, 2019). Sheridan's scale 7 items are the following:

Statistical reliability (lack of error)

Usefulness (ability of the system to do what is most important)

Robustness (ability and flexibility of the system to perform variations of the task)

Understandability (transparency of the system in revealing how and why it is doing what it is doing)

Explication of intent (communication to the trustee what the system will do next)

Familiarity (based on the user's past experience of the system)

¹ Sheridan, T. B. (2019). Extending Three Existing Models to Analysis of Trust in Automation: Signal Detection, Statistical Parameter Estimation, and Model-Based Control. *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 61(7), 1162–1170.

Dependence (from the trustee’s point of view, as compared to other ways of doing the task).

Sheridan’s scale contains both elements referred to the robot than to the human, allowing for a combined measurement of human trust against the system trustworthiness. Higher level of trust does not mean a better system implementation, but an optimal balance between human trust and system trustworthiness needs to be the target. Poor calibration can lead to loss of safety (due to overconfident misuse), or loss of productivity (due to underconfident disuse).

Cognitive Load

Cognitive load is related to the amount of attentional or working memory (WM) resources needed to solve a task (Just et al., 2003). Existing scales are the Ayres index (2006) the Paas scale (Paas et al., 2003), NASA TLX (Colligan, et al., 2015), see Subjective Workload Assessment Technique as well, and Rating Scale Mental Effort. As it is the most used metrics in the field, the selected scale for the evaluation of Cognitive Load in ShareWork is the NASA TLX. Note that cognitive load is both task specific (complex tasks are more likely to carry mental workload) and subject dependent (expert have lower scores than novice).

Situational Awareness

Situation awareness is defined as “the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning, and the projection of their status in the near future” (Endsley, 1995). As for cognitive load, situation awareness differs among individuals as a function of task expertise, as a more experienced worker is able to perform the same task with lower cognitive load and higher situational awareness than a less experienced worker. Endsley identifies three levels of situation awareness: perception, comprehension, and projection. The most used instrument in the field is the SAGAT (Situational Awareness Global Assessment Technique) developed by Endsley in 1988, and it will be used in the evaluation of Situational Awareness in ShareWork.

The measurement and evaluation of the three human-factors KPIs will be performed through questionnaires and interviews to the operators, similarly to the preliminary one performed in the first months of the project and detailed in D6.1. The interviews will be conducted using tablets and Qualtrics, with the exact software to be discussed together with the end users. The human workers will be able to give answers on a sliding scale that will be translated into a numerical value (1 to 10 rating scale) for the statistical analysis.

To the best extent, compatibly with the project development and the final tests execution, the evolution of human factors will be monitored in the ongoing course of the project, by following progress in terms of trust for the technical modules most directly related with human experience. In this regards, it has already been planned a first round of data acquisition with LMS for the AR interfaces and with CNR for the task planner. Evolving versions of the prototypes will be compared for each module and across the three dimensions (trust, situational awareness, cognitive load), thereby guiding the development of each module to optimize trust, maximize situational awareness and minimize cognitive load.

While this approach is applicable for specific modules, the complete sharework system will be tested at the industrial premises only in the final months of the project. Therefore, two different approaches have been foreseen, depending on the possibilities available during the final tests

execution. If possible, the same operator will perform multiple interviews as the time passed testing the system increases, in order to record the evolution of trust, cognitive load and situational awareness as he gains more experience with the system. If not possible, the operators will be interviewed only after a set number of hours spent using the system. In both cases, the methodology applied for the interviews will be the same and are the ones presented above.

Concerning the analysis of trust in specific, the standard cross plotting approach for the Sheridan scale will be followed, allowing for the comparison of objective trustworthiness of the robot and the subjective trust of the operator, leading to the detection of false positive and false negative and cases of over-trusting (danger of misuse) and under-trusting (danger of disuse). In addition, to provide a standard for the trust scale, STRANE will conduct an exhaustive meta-analysis of empirical data with methods employing the Sheridan scale. Using classical statistical analysis, STRANE will compute a trust standard based on existing studies, which will provide the ground for 1) a standard for comparing the Sharework results with state-of-the-art results and 2) a proposition for a trust standard with important consequences for human factors.

Due to the complexity and the multifaceted aspects of human-factors in collaborative robotics, which are dependent on the task, on the worker experience and personality and on many other factors, both objective and subjective, specific targets for these KPIs are not defined here. Rather, the proposed methodology has been detailed and will act as a precise and structured guideline to guide the evaluation process of human-factors in the four industrial scenarios. The collected data will then need to be processed and analysed, in order to allow for the extraction of valuable information that will both guide module development and comprehensively describe human-factors in each use case.

3.2 Ergonomics assessment

The Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) has been selected as a common methodology to evaluate the exposure of individual workers to ergonomic risk factors in the four use cases of the ShareWork project. The RULA ergonomic assessment tool uses a systematic process to evaluate the postural load requirements of a specific task on the neck, trunk and upper extremities. The ergonomics assessment is performed on a single frame of the task executed, meaning that it is required to identify the most critical moment in the task execution and evaluate the posture of the person in that frame. The result of the RULA assessment is a score from 1 to 7, with the lower value indicating a lower risk level of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), as shown in the table below.

Score	Level of MSD Risk
1-2	negligible risk, no action required
3-4	low risk, change may be needed
5-6	medium risk, further investigation, change soon
6+	very high risk, implement change now

The RULA assessment tool is, therefore, a simple and user-friendly tool that requires minimal time, effort, and equipment, enabling the identification of the muscular effort which is associated with working postures and excessive forces while performing static or repetitive work. In addition, the simple scoring method makes it easy to identify the urgency for a task reorganization. For the ShareWork project, it is foreseen to reduce the RULA index score of all tasks to less than 2, thanks to the implementation of optimal human-robot collaboration. Nevertheless, the RULA assessment tool also has some limitations:

- 1) Has a strong focus on posture, but a weak focus on force, repetition and duration of the task. It also does not consider the available recovery time or hand-arm vibration.
- 2) Only allows to assess the operator's posture at one point in time, requiring a new assessment for any different posture the evaluator wants to analyse.
- 3) Requires separate assessment of right and left sides of the body.

For such reasons, when defining the KPIs for the operators' ergonomics assessment, the RULA score will be paired with two additional KPIs that will take into account the amount of time that the operator has to perform high load or repetitive low load actions.

3.3 KPIs for Goizper scenario

Following a continuous discussion process with Goizper team to enable the correct implementation of the ShareWork system in their manufacturing process, two of the three scenarios described in D1.2 have been selected, namely the rotary table bolts tightening and the cam followers visual inspection. The Locking Ring bolts tightening task has been removed due the impossibility to find an electrical screwdriver capable to provide the required torque within the available narrow space of the locking ring. More details on the Goizper tasks and ShareWork system layouts are provided in D1.5.

The KPIs for the two tasks scenarios are presented below and, for each scenario, the step by step descriptions of the actions required to complete the collaborative tasks are presented. In the step by step table, the following abbreviations have been used:

- **H:** The action is performed by a human
- **R:** The action is performed by a robot
- **HRC:** The action is performed by a human and the robot collaboratively
- **H-R:** Two separate actions are performed by a human and the robot in parallel
- **H/R:** The action can be performed alternatively by a human or the robot

3.3.1 Rotary table bolts tightening KPIs

Table 2: Goizper – Rotary table bolts tightening step by step task execution sequence

H/R	OPERATOR	TOOL	ROBOT	TOOL
H	Set the rotary table on the hydraulic table		Rest position	
H	Mount correct bit on the tightening tool			
H	Select the robot program	HR interfaces		

H	Put adhesive and introduce Bolt 1	Adhesive + Allen key		
H	Put adhesive and introduce Bolt 2 (clockwise/counterclockwise)	Adhesive + Allen key		
H	Put adhesive and introduce Bolt 3 (clockwise/counterclockwise)	Adhesive + Allen key		
HRC	Command to the Cobot to start task	HR interfaces	Start from bolt 1	Electrical screwdriver
HRC	Put adhesive and introduce Bolt X (clockwise/counterclockwise)	Adhesive + Allen key	Tighten all bolts in clockwise/counterclockwise order, applying the 30% of the required torque	
H-R	Visual quality inspection		Tighten again all bolts applying the 100% of the required torque	Electrical screwdriver
H-R	Get ready for next assembly task		Signal correct operations/errors to the operator	HR interfaces
H-R	Move on to following tasks		Move to rest position	

Table 3: Goizper – Rotary table bolts tightening KPIs

KPI	Description	Measure Unit	Baseline	Target
Robot Utilization	Time cobot is active in bolt screwing activity compared to total time for bolts positioning + screwing operation	%	-	60%
Robot Wait Time	Total time the cobot has to wait for the operator to place the screws	%	-	50%
Cycle Time	Estimated max time for bolts positioning + screwing time for a pattern of N bolts	s	15*N	60+10*N
Robot Performances	Actual average cycle time vs planned cycle time	%	-	120%
Max torque for M10 bolts	Torque required to fix M10 bolts correctly	Nm	69Nm	69Nm
Max torque for M12 bolts	Torque required to fix M12 bolts correctly	Nm	120Nm	120Nm
Quality	Bolts correctly fixed vs total bolts fixed	%	100%	98%
Set-Up Time	Total time needed to fully prepare the system to perform the process	s	-	120s
Training Hours	Average time required to train the operator	minutes	15min	60min

Unit Cost	Estimation of unit cost with cobot vs unit cost with manual work	%	-	95-100%
Reportable Health & Safety incidents	Baseline: Reportable incidents to operators Target: Human-Robot collisions + near misses	Number per month	0	0
Reportable Environmental Incidents	Baseline: Reportable damages to parts or tools Target: Robot-Environment collisions	Number per month	0	0
Ergonomics Evaluation - High Loads	The operator is required to perform high load tasks (120Nm bolts tightening)	% of cycle time	10%	0%
Ergonomics Evaluation – Repetitive tasks	The operator is required to perform repetitive low load tasks (bolts insertion and turning)	% of cycle time	50%	25%
Ergonomics Evaluation - RULA	RULA index in the operation for the average height operator	RULA index	3	2

3.3.2 Cam followers visual inspection KPIs

Table 4: Goizper – Cam followers visual inspection step by step task execution sequence

H/R	OPERATOR	TOOL	ROBOT	TOOL
H	Assemble the rotary table		System in rest position	
H	Set the rotary table on the hydraulic table			
H	Couple servomotor system with the cam shaft			
H-R	Move in front of cam openings		Be ready for commands	
H-R	Command the system to start task	HR Interfaces	Start Quality Inspection task	
HRC	Command rotation speed, acceleration and direction	Joystick / Gesture	Rotate shaft following operators command (changing speed, accelerations and direction). Show torque value constantly.	
HRC	Check the rotation of the cam followers			
HRC	Stop rotation if needed	HR Interfaces		
HRC	Command rotation speed, acceleration and direction	Joystick / Gesture		
HRC	Check the rotation of the cam followers			
H-R	Finalize inspection		Stop servomotor	
H	Decouple shaft and wait for next task		System in rest position	

Table 5: Goizper – Cam followers visual inspection KPIs

KPI	Description	Measure Unit	Baseline	Target
Robot Utilization	Time robot is active in shaft rotation vs total time for quality inspection	%	-	75%
Robot Wait Time	Total time the system has to wait for the operator to complete coupling with the rotary system	s	-	180s
Cycle Time	Estimated total time for a complete quality inspection	minutes	60min	45min
Robot Performances	Actual average cycle time vs planned cycle time	%	-	130%
Max torque	Max torque the tool can apply on the shaft to rotate it	Nm	-	200Nm
Quality	Operator inputs correctly interpreted (stop, faster, slower, change direction, etc.) vs total received operator inputs	%	-	95%
Set-Up Time	Total time needed to fully prepare the system to perform the process (after coupling with the shaft)	s	-	30s
Training Hours	Average time required to train the operator	minutes	15min	60min
Unit Cost	Estimation of unit cost with cobot vs unit cost with manual work	%	-	90-95%
Reportable Health & Safety incidents	Baseline: Reportable incidents to operators Target: Human-Robot collisions + near misses	Number per month	0	0
Reportable Environmental Incidents	Baseline: Reportable damages to parts or tools Target: Robot-Environment collisions	Number per month	0	0
Ergonomics Evaluation - High Loads	The operator is required to perform high loads tasks (shaft rotation, avg=100Nm, peak=200Nm)	% of cycle time	90%	0%
Ergonomics evaluation – RULA	RULA index in the operation for the average height operator	RULA index	4	2

3.4 KPIs for Nissan scenario

Nissan use case scenario deals with the passenger door assembly on vehicle cab, besides a series of tasks at the pick-up's bed. The details of the task execution foreseen in Nissan scenario remain as described in D1.2.

Table 6: Nissan – Step by step task execution sequence

H/R	OPERATOR	TOOL	ROBOT	TOOL
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R			Robot approaching front door fixture	
R			Front door grasping	Robot gripper
R			Fixture door unclamping	Door fixture
H-R	Approaching front door		Robot transferring front door to chassis	Robot gripper
H	Connecting harness			
H	Positioning finetuning			
H	Pre-setting of nuts			
H	Picking of wrench	Wrench 1		
H	Securing of nuts	Wrench 1		
H	Placing of wrench	Wrench 1		
HRC	Positioning finetuning			
H	Picking of HCT	HCT		
H	Securing of screw	HCT		
H	Placing of HTC	HCT		
H	Picking of wrench for bed assembly	Wrench 2		
H-R	Walking to bed		Robot Releasing of front door	Gripper
H-R	Setting of channel at bed	Wrench 2	Robot approaching back door fixture	
R			Back door grasping	Gripper
R			Back door fixture unclamping	Door fixture
H-R	Approaching back door		Transferring back door to chassis	Gripper
H-R	Connecting of harness			
HRC	Positioning finetuning			
H	Pre-setting of nuts			
H	Picking of wrench	Wrench 1		
H	Securing of nuts	Wrench 1		
H	Placing of wrench	Wrench 1		
HRC	Positioning finetuning			
H	Picking of HCT	HCT		
H	Securing of screw	HCT		
H	Placing of HTC	HCT		
H-R	Walking to bed		Robot Releasing of back door	Gripper
R			Robot returning to home position	

Table 7: Nissan – Industrial impact KPIs

KPI	Description	Measure Unit	Baseline	Target
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Robot Utilization	Time robot runs a program compared to total cycle time	%	-	60%
Robot Efficiency	Time robot is in motion compared to time robot runs a program	%	-	50%
Robot Wait Time	Time robot is not performing productive work compared to time robot runs a program	%	-	50%
Cycle Time	Duration of the assembly operations for both doors	S	180s	120s
Robot Performances	Actual cycle time vs planned cycle time	%	-	98%
Set-Up Time	Total time needed to fully prepare the system to perform the process	minutes	-	5 min
Training Hours	Average time required to train the operator	hours	15h	2h
Reportable Health & Safety incidents	Human-Robot collisions + near misses	Number per month	0	0
Reportable Environmental Incidents	Robot-Environment collisions	Number per month	0	0
Medium time between failure	Medium time between system failure	minutes	800min	400min
Medium time to repair	Medium time required to repair the system in case of a failure	minutes	5min	5min
Ergonomics Evaluation - High Loads	The operator is required to perform high loads tasks (bad posture during nuts and bolts preset, tight, and harness connection)	% of cycle time	30%	20%
Ergonomics Evaluation – Repetitive tasks	The operator is required to perform repetitive low loads tasks (operator hoist movement)	% of cycle time	15%	0%
Ergonomics evaluation – RULA	RULA index in the operation for the average height operator	RULA index	2	1

3.5 KPIs for Alstom scenario

Following a continuous and iterative discussion process with ALSTOM team, to enable the correct implementation of the ShareWork system in their manufacturing process, the silicone

application and the rivetting scenarios described in D1.2 have been selected. More details are provided in D1.5.

Table 8: Alstom – Step by step task execution sequence

H/R	OPERATOR	TOOL	ROBOT	TOOL
H	Position structure 0-3			
H-R	Position structure 1-2		Detect structure type	
H	Clean surface 0	Cloth		
H	Clean surface 1	Cloth		
H-R	Clean surface 2	Cloth	Apply silicone 0	Silicone Gun
H-R	Clean surface 3	Cloth	Apply silicone 1	Silicone Gun
H-R	Spread silicone 0	Spatula	Apply silicone 2	Silicone Gun
H-R	Spread silicone 1	Spatula	Apply silicone 3	Silicone Gun
H	Spread silicone 2	Spatula		
H	Spread silicone 3	Spatula		
H	Position structure 0-1			
H	Insert rivets 0			
H	Insert rivets 1			
H	Close station fixtures 0-1			
H-R	Position structure 2-3		Riveting 0	Riveting tool
H-R	Insert rivets 2		Riveting 1	Riveting tool
H	Insert rivets 3			
H	Close station fixtures 2-3			
H-R	Quality inspection 0	Dedicated tool	Riveting 2	Riveting tool
H-R	Quality inspection 1	Dedicated tool	Riveting 3	Riveting tool
H	Quality inspection 2	Dedicated tool		
H	Quality inspection 3	Dedicated tool		

Table 9: Alstom - Industrial impact KPIs

KPI	Description	Measure Unit	Baseline	Target
Robot Utilization	Time robot runs a program compared to total cycle time	%	-	30%
Robot Efficiency	Time robot is in motion compared to time robot runs a program	%	-	90%
Robot Wait Time	Time robot is not performing productive work compared to time robot runs a program	%	-	10%
Cycle Time	Duration of the assembly operation for 1 lateral frame	minutes	20min	16min

Robot Performances	Actual cycle time vs planned cycle time	%	-	120%
Quality	Error and faults during operation	number	0	0
Set-Up Time	Total time needed to fully prepare the system to perform the process	minutes	-	4min
Training Hours	Average time required to train the operator to work with the robot	hours	-	2h
Training	Needs for training for special riveting process	Y/N	Yes	No
Reportable Health & Safety incidents	Baseline: Reportable incidents to operators Target: Human-Robot collisions + near misses	Number per month	no data	0
Reportable Environmental Incidents	Baseline: Reportable damages to parts or tools Target: Robot-Environment collisions	Number per month	0	0
Ergonomics Evaluation - High Loads	The operator is required to perform high loads tasks (riveting and positioning the metallic part on the table)	% of cycle time	43%	27%
Ergonomics Evaluation – Repetitive tasks	The operator is required to perform repetitive low loads tasks (rivets insertion and spreading the silicone)	% of cycle time	16%	12%
Ergonomics Evaluation	RULA index in the operation for the average height operator	RULA index	3	2

3.6 KPIs for Cembre scenario

In Cembre’s use case, the main expected result achieved with the implementation of the ShareWork system is an improvement of the human operators’ ergonomics, leading to better working conditions and an improved job competitiveness. In order to measure objectively the ergonomics improvement, its evaluation has been reparametrized to allow pairing it with the evaluation of the manufacturing costs of the human-robot collaborative system. The definition process for Cembre’s KPIs has therefore been guided mainly by the evaluation of the economic impact of the implementation of the ShareWork technologies.

Two economic indexes of utmost importance have therefore been considered: the *direct costs*, as personnel costs, HW depreciation, usage costs and the *indirect costs*, as the improvement of the human ergonomics. In particular, for the direct costs, the following has been considered:

Logistic Cell Cap Cost: 4.5€/hour (60Month depreciation, 22days/Month, 16hours/day)

Human Cost: approx. 30€/hour

On the other side, for the indirect cost, the *ergonomic load* on the human worker has been considered and parametrized. The ergonomic load has been defined as a weight (≥ 1) that will multiply the human cost. A value of 1 indicates a light operation for the worker that does not present any ergonomic stress, therefore not increasing the human nominal cost. Values greater than 1 indicate the presence of some ergonomic stress for the human worker. The larger the number, the higher the ergonomic stress and, as a consequence, the higher will be the cost of manual labor. This parametrization of the ergonomic load as a factor that increases the human cost serve the purpose to represent the inefficiency due to possible musculoskeletal disease, or the decrease of the human efficiency due to the ergonomic load of the task. It will then be possible to schedule the execution of tasks dividing the work between the human worker and the robot with the objective of minimizing the final cost, resulting also in a minimization of human ergonomic stress.

In the table below, multiple actions are indicated as alternative between human and robot, to represent the scheduling process described above. Depending on each specific part and the corresponding evaluation of robot costs and human costs (with ergonomic load weight), the action will be assigned. Cembre foresee that at least three components will be available in the logistic station at the same time, and human/robot can work in parallel on different items, in order to optimize the usage of resources.

Table 10: Cembre - Step by step task execution sequence

H/R	OPERATOR	TOOL	ROBOT	TOOL
H	Check dimensions	Visual inspection		
H	Check diameter of holes	Micrometer		
H	Check holes position	Caliber		
H	Check dimension of the slot	Caliber		
H	Check chamfer	Visual inspection		
H/R	Unscrew bolts	Electric Wrench	Unscrew bolts	
H/R	Move the bracket away	Hand	Move the bracket away	Gripper
H/R	Extract the part	Hand	Extract the part	Gripper
H/R	Place the part in the box	Hand	Place the part in the box	Gripper
H/R	Clean the surface of the fixtures	Tissue	Clean the surface of the fixtures	Air pressure
H/R	Pick a raw part from the box	Hand	Pick a raw part from the box	Gripper
H/R	Insert the part in the fixtures	Hand	Insert the part in the fixtures	Gripper
H/R	Move the bracket over the part	Hand	Move the bracket over the part	Gripper
H/R	Tightening bolt	Hand	Tightening bolt	Gripper

The KPI presented in the table below will be computed considering the production of at least three different batches of three items each. This computation will be driven by the fact that the

savings and improvement of performances may vary according to the actual item to be assembled.

Table 11: Cembre - Industrial impact KPIs

KPI	Description	Measure Unit	Baseline	Target
Robot Utilization	Time robot runs a program compared to total time the logistic cell is used	%	-	100%
Robot Efficiency	The robot is performing a task in parallel or interacting with the human vs total cycle time	%	-	50%
Cycle Time	Time for complete HRC assembly (using scheduler and motion planning) vs time for complete manual assembly	%	-	75%
Robot Performances	Actual average cycle time vs planned cycle time	%	-	100%
Quality	Number of scrap parts	%	0.5%	0.05%
Training Hours	Average time required to train the operator	weeks	2	1
Time to Prototype	Time required to engineer and to commission a new part type	weeks	4	3
Cost to ramp-up	Estimation of the cost to move from prototype to production	€	50.000€	25.000€
Cost to items	The costs is calculated considering the sum of the economic cost for each production step, computed as in the previous table. The KPI is therefore defined as the reduction of the cost of a percentage, considering the mean production costs for three different items. The baseline is computed considering that all the operations are performed by the human operator	%	-	-30%
Job competitiveness	Increase in the number of engineers involved in production with respect to the number of technicians	%	-	+25%
Lot lead time	Time each lot spend inside the shop floor	days	30	24
Reportable Health & Safety incidents	Baseline: Reportable incidents to operators Target: Human-Robot collisions + near misses	Number per month	0	0
Reportable Environmental Incidents	Baseline: Reportable damages to parts or tools Target: Robot-Environment collisions	Number per month	1	0

Ergonomics Evaluation - High Loads	The operator is required to perform high loads tasks (bolts tightening on 2 to 5kg parts; motion of 15kg boxes with rough and waste material)	% of cycle time	15%	7.5% (-50%)
Ergonomics Evaluation – Repetitive tasks	The operator is required to perform repetitive low loads tasks (small parts and tools motion to and from LUS)	% of cycle time	25%	6.5% (-75%)
Ergonomics Evaluation - RULA	RULA index in the operation for the average height operator	RULA index	2	1

4 KPIs for modules evaluation

In this section, KPIs for module evaluation are described. The evaluation of dedicate KPIs for each module will allow to assess the performances of the ShareWork system under multiple points of view, in order to ensure that all components of the system perform correctly towards the manufacturing goals and to identify the source of any possible issue and fix it.

Starting from the basis of D1.6, each module is here briefly presented, focusing on its objectives, the current state of the art and methodologies available for its performance's evaluation. As a direct consequence, a table of specific KPIs is presented, providing the metric description, the target to be achieved by the ShareWork system and the current baseline, representing state-of-the-art algorithms or practices or related industrial standards. When the definition of a baseline of a target is currently not possible, due to lack of data or the specificity of the addressed task, it is motivated and the foreseen methodology for the evaluation of the proposed metrics is detailed nonetheless.

The schematic presentation of all modules, their purpose and role, is presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Modules role and WP

Module framework	Modules		WP
Perception	#1	Knowledge base	WP2
	#2	Environment cognition	WP2
	#3	Human tracking	WP2
	#4	Primitives learning	WP2
	#5	Human task identification	WP2
Motion Planning	#6	Human-aware dynamic planning and scheduling for HRC tasks	WP3
	#7	Offline and real-time human-aware and safe robot motion planning	WP3
	#8	Robot motion planning based on learning from demonstration	WP3
HR Communication	#9	Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication	WP4

Safety and security	#10	Human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative high-payload robots	WP5
	#11	Tooling adaptation for safe HRC	WP5
	#12	Data security	WP5
Human Factors	#13	Continuous evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction	WP4
	#14	Operator training through AR	WP6

In the following sections, each technological module of the ShareWork system is detailed and its related KPIs are presented.

4.1 Module #1: Knowledge Base

This module aims to design and develop a Knowledge Base (KB) capable of supporting all the cognitive processes involved in the Sharework control system designed according to an ad-hoc domain ontology, called Sharwork Ontology for Human Robot Collaboration (SOHO), capable of defining the general concepts, properties and relationships that hold in collaborative manufacturing scenarios. SOHO design takes inspiration from two particularly relevant ontologies defined for robotics and automation and sensor networks: the CORA ontology and the SSN ontology. CORA is the IEEE standard ontology for robotics and automation. SSN is the W3C standard ontology for IoT devices and sensor network. Thus, SOHO ontology relies on many of the concepts defined by CORA and SSN. These concepts are integrated and extended into the Sharework ontology, using a uniform theoretical foundation through a selected upper ontology.

The KB will characterize all the information needed to interpret human instructions/commands, interpret the status of the work-cell and the status of the human operators, recognize production processes and automatically generate collaborative tasks accordingly. Moreover, the objective of the module is to realize a set of knowledge processing mechanisms capable of dynamically infer new knowledge, guarantying the continuous update of the KB over time. In this way, the control system will always have an updated control model.

In order to evaluate the performance and, also, the effectiveness of the module, two different perspectives will be considered:

- *Modeling perspective*: the KB will be designed upon a dedicated ontology (specifically defined for Sharework) capable of representing all the use cases of the pilots as well as all the relevant human-robot collaboration aspects of the modeled processes. Under this terms, the module will influence all the parameters reflecting the representational capabilities such as, e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, etc.
- *Reasoning perspective*: a set of knowledge processing mechanisms must maintain correctness and validity of the KB over time. The main KPI of the inference processes is related to Efficiency and must be comparable with the latencies of the production environment.

The KPI considered for this module are the following:

- **Representation accuracy:** this is to assess the ability of the KB (and the Ontology) to capture all the information needed to represent the collaborative cell. It is hard to quantitatively measure the representation power of a KB but we will consider appropriate to represent in the KB all the key components for supporting HRC. In pilots, the target is to have a 90% satisfaction of end users about modeling capabilities.
- **KB storage/query requests management:** This is to measure the time spent by the KB module system to manage storage/query requests. The KB module will operate with a latency of few seconds, i.e., with a latency compatible with robot cycle time.
- **KB inference process:** This is to measure the time spent to infer new knowledge from the KB. Also, this functionality of the KB module will operate with a latency compatible with robot cycle time.

The latencies considered for KB module processes are domain dependent and cannot be precisely quantified. In previous applications, the same technology has been proved to be suitable for deployment in realistic scenarios².

Table 13: Knowledge Base KPIs

KPIs	Representation accuracy	KB storage/query requests management	KB inference process
DESCRIPTION	Ability of the KB to capture all the information needed to represent the collaborative cell	Time spent to manage KB storage/query requests	Time spent to infer new knowledge from the KB
MEASURE UNIT	qualitative measure	seconds	seconds
BASELINE	domain dependent	domain dependent	domain dependent
TARGET (GOIZPER)	Representing key components for supporting HRC	compatible with robot cycle	compatible with robot cycle
TARGET (NISSAN)	Representing key components for supporting HRC	compatible with robot cycle	compatible with robot cycle
TARGET (ALSTOM)	Representing key components for supporting HRC	compatible with robot cycle	compatible with robot cycle
TARGET (CEMBRE)	Representing key components for supporting HRC	compatible with robot cycle	compatible with robot cycle

4.2 Module #2: Environment Cognition

² A Umbrico, A Cesta, G Cortellessa, A Orlandini. A Holistic Approach to Behavior Adaptation for Socially Assistive Robots. International Journal of Social Robotics. 2020.

S Borgo, A Cesta, A Orlandini, A Umbrico. Knowledge-based adaptive agents for manufacturing domains. Engineering with Computers 35 (3), 755-779. 2019.

In this module a general semantic cognition method will be developed, which enables the vision network to detect certain objects and classify them using a unique identifier. For classification, machine learning approaches will be used. These algorithms have to be taught on the specific use case in order to achieve a satisfactory level of confidence. Therefore, this module requires training data from the different use case owners in form of CAD and/or image/video data.

The vision system will be set up in such a way, that the field of vision is blocked as less as possible. In order to allow a certain level of reliability and redundancy the system is projected to cover the desired objects with at least two homogenous sensors. This module has high requirements regarding resolution and accuracy of the classified and segmented objects, as these are used in high-level tasks.

Further the module will provide following outputs:

- Point clouds of segmented objects
- Object labels (e.g. tool, item, etc.)
- Centre of mass of each object
- All data can be forwarded to the knowledge base

This is based on following input data:

- 3D-camera network providing individual point cloud scans
- Absolute pose of the sensors according to a general reference frame

Different indicators have been defined to examine this module:

- *Classifier Accuracy*: Classifier accuracy is defined by the correctly labeled and detected objects referred to the overall count of segmented objects, e.g. if four objects are segmented and two are labeled correctly, the labeling accuracy is 50%.
- *Segmentor Accuracy*: Segmentor accuracy is defined by the correctly segmented process relevant objects referred to the real count of process relevant objects in the environment, e.g. if four objects are distributed throughout the environment and three of them are segmented correctly, the segmentor accuracy is 75%.
- *Computational Efficiency*: Computational efficiency is the measure of the mean cycle time of the full process. This means the time it takes to fully segment and classify a single sensor network reading.

Table 14: Environment Cognition KPIs

KPIs	Segmentor Accuracy	Classifier Accuracy	Computational Efficiency
DESCRIPTION	Rate of correctly found items in the workspace	Rate of correctly labeled items in the set of segmented items	Mean cycle time while segmenting and classifying a single frame of the vision network
MEASURE UNIT	%	%	ms
BASELINE	No baseline	94.7% (on perfect data)	No baseline

TARGET (GOIZPER)	35%	70%	< 2000ms
TARGET (NISSAN)	35%	70%	< 2000ms
TARGET (ALSTOM)	30%	65%	< 2000ms
TARGET (CEMBRE)	35%	70%	< 2000ms

In order to explain the base or the assessed KPIs, it is necessary to differentiate between the overall workspace that is covered by the cameras and the task workspace that includes the task to be performed. In the use-cases the cameras are distributed over an area of at least 5 by 5 meters up to side lengths of over 20 meters. This means that this module has to deal with large scaling differences. As some of the required items are so small that it is impossible to detect them given the circumstances, they will be excluded from evaluation, e.g. rivets in the Alstom use case, as the object at 5-10m range will vanish in the noise of the sensor. The Alstom use-case as a whole is far more challenging, due to its large space to be covered and the sparsity of possible mounting spots. Thus, the KPIs are slightly lowered.

Segmenting objects in an unsupervised fashion is a very challenging task, as no references are known from the environment. Such approaches can only be based on density distribution, contours and/or dynamic states. Further, these approaches are heavily influenced by noise in the camera readings. The noise again is amplified with raising range. Thus, the use-cases establish extremely challenging situations for this sub-module. Most unsupervised segmentation was developed for 2D images, thus there is no real benchmark for 3D unsupervised bulge segmentation in low time. As two good 2D references IIC operates on the CIFAR-10 data set with 61.7% accuracy, while SegSort achieves 55.86% on the PASCAL VOC 2012 data set. Both algorithms only operate on 2D data and are based on neural networks. Both algorithms are unlikely to operate in online time.

For the classifier accuracy, 3D classification benchmarks exist, e.g. semantic-8. Here, the neural network based approach achieves an accuracy of up to 94.7% with a cycle time of 1s (GeomAdapt). The semantic-8 benchmark has high resolution point clouds annotated each, which makes it very powerful for supervised learning approaches. In the use-cases training data is very sparse, as it can only be based on rough data (CAD, images) and is projected to not be satisfactory for high accuracy classification. Further, the segmented point clouds from the segmentor sub-module are projected to be subpar compared to the clean benchmark. Consequently, the system is projected to achieve lower accuracy scores than benchmarks. Our aim is to develop a system available for real world workspace surveillance. This is only partly comparable to clean and theoretical values as achieved in benchmarks. However, the system is projected to yield satisfactory accuracy.

4.3 Module #3: Human Tracking

Human tracking is the process of locating humans over time using one or multiple cameras. To perform this tracking this module will analyse sequential video frames and create a trajectory. This means that we can divide the whole process in two basic steps: detection and location in one frame, and tracking using information from all frames. As a result, performance indicators in this module will be divided in two steps, Frame-based metrics and Tracking-based metrics, which are detailed below.

4.3.1 Frame-based metrics

The frame-based metrics will be used to evaluate the human detection performance on individual frames. A Ground Truth Image Set containing humans will be created. This set will have to be general and robust enough, which implies that different environments, actions, lighting conditions, occlusions will be taken into account when defining the set. Moreover, frames without any human will be added to the set. For each frame human positions will be labelled.

For the metric provided in the table below, the following acronyms are used:

- TP = True Positive
- FP = False Positive
- TN = True Negative
- FN = False Negative
- GT = Ground Truth (total number of identification)

More details are provided in D1.6.

Table 15: Human Tracking, Frame-based KPIs

KPIs	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Detection rate	False Alarm rate
DESCRIPTION	Accuracy = $(TP+TN) / GT$	Precision = $TP / (TP + FP)$	Recall = $TP / (TP + FN)$	DR = $TP / (TP + FN)$	FAR = $FP / (TP + FP)$
MEASURE UNIT	%	%	%	%	%
BASELINE	75%	65%	75%	75%	35%
TARGET (GOIZPER)	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%
TARGET (NISSAN)	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%
TARGET (ALSTOM)	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%
TARGET (CEMBRE)	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%

4.3.2 Tracking-based metrics

The tracking-based metrics measure the ability to track humans over time. As in the previous case, a Ground Truth Video Set containing humans moving in videos will be created. Moreover, this set will also have to be general and robust enough. For each frame from each video human positions will be labelled, so that a complete track is obtained.

At this point, it is important to consider how well the tracker estimates the exact positions of the human along all the video. That means how different is a correctly detected track from what we expected. Therefore, there is the need of another set of important metrics which focus on the quality of the tracking. It is important to remark that these indicators will measure the quality of a single track so statistical analysis of all samples will have to be done to have a general view.

- **Track Matching Error:** it measures error between the obtained track and its corresponding one at the Ground Truth Set by calculating the average distance error in all frames;
- **Track Completeness:** it is defined as the time the obtained track overlaps with the Ground Truth Set track divided by the total duration of the track;
- **Track Detection Latency:** it is the time delay of the obtained track start compared to the Ground Truth Set track start.

Table 16: Human Tracking, Tracking-based KPIs

KPIs	Track Matching Error	Track Completeness	Track Detection Latency
DESCRIPTION	Avg distance error in all frames	Time the obtained track overlaps with GT vs total time of the track	Time delay of the obtained track start compared to the GT Set track start
MEASURE UNIT	mm	%	ms
BASELINE	100 (with a single camera at 4 m)	70%	1000
TARGET (GOIZPER)	10	80%	50
TARGET (NISSAN)	10	80%	50
TARGET (ALSTOM)	10	80%	50
TARGET (CEMBRE)	10	80%	50

All these KPIs have been thought to be analysed using only images, i.e. 2D detection and tracking. However, if human 3D information is available in GT set (for example using extra sensors to obtain this information), all metrics can be used in the same way to measure the performance of the system not only in images but in 3D.

It is also important to remark that both frame-based and tracking-based metrics can be applied to specific parts of the human skeleton that will be detected. For example, if it is considered that it is relevant to the project having the information of the hand, the same analysis can be done.

We have defined many indicators and proposed a target for all of them. Accuracy in our dataset (from different use cases) must be higher than current accuracy of the state-of-the-art algorithms in general datasets (60-80%), so at least 80% of accuracy should be reached. Moreover, the system should be able to process more than 20 frames per second to ensure a real time solution. This implies that image resolutions will be adapted, if necessary, to fit time requirements.

4.4 Module #4: Primitives Learning

Motion primitives learning module takes as input the human tracking trajectories and object segmentation and translate them into useful features for both human task identification and safe motion planning modules. In particular, the motion primitives learning algorithm segments

the trajectories with a semantic understanding and build motion primitives that represent these segments. Later, these learned primitives can be applied to predict complete human trajectories from partially observed trajectories.

The metrics of the segmentation and motion primitives building cannot be evaluated independently as this module interacts constantly with Human Task Identification module and different modules in Task and motion planning for HR cooperation work package. For such reasons, the evaluation of the proposed metrics is dependent on the relations between these modules.

Moreover, the quality of the results highly depends on the dataset that will be studied and, therefore, specific improvement targets are hard to define if it is not yet defined in which dataset our models will be compared. In T2.4, SEDS and CLF-DM motion primitives are considered as the State of Art models and the objective is, therefore, to push our model to outperform their metrics. In this sense, we have observed that our model improves by 50% over the LASA dataset. Further information can be found in the paper “*ImitationFlows : Learning Deep Stable Stochastic Dynamic Systems by Normalizing Flows*” attached to the D2.4. This paper presents TUDA’s main results in primitives learning and a further comparison with the State of Art models.

Table 17: Primitives Learning KPIs

KPIs	Swept Area Error	Frechet Distance
DESCRIPTION	Area Between demonstrated trajectories and generated ones	Disparity between demonstrated trajectories and generated ones
MEASURE UNIT	mm ²	mm
BASELINE	SEDS	SEDS
TARGET (GOIZPER)	outperform SoA in 50%	outperform SoA in 50%
TARGET (NISSAN)	outperform SoA in 50%	outperform SoA in 50%
TARGET (ALSTOM)	outperform SoA in 50%	outperform SoA in 50%
TARGET (CEMBRE)	outperform SoA in 50%	outperform SoA in 50%

4.5 Module #5: Human Task Identification

Human Task identification is the process of identifying what a human is doing. The input of this module will be the primitives obtained in the previous one, which means that, to evaluate the performance of this module, we will work only with validated primitives. We will not consider inputs with errors as we want to evaluate the module separately. In case we wanted to use this module to analyse primitives learning performance, all inputs should be considered.

The key definitions explained before are also valid for this module and most of the metrics will be used to measure its performance. Moreover, the number of actions to identify is an important metric to evaluate as the rest of indicators will depend on this parameter.

- Number of actions;
- Accuracy;
- Precision;
- Recall;

- Detection Rate;
- False Alarm Rate.

As in the human tracking module, we have defined many indicators and it is difficult to define a target for all of them. We will focus on number of actions detected and accuracy. More than 15 different actions should be identified and accuracy in our dataset (from different use cases) must be higher than 80% identifying different actions defined in Sharework.

Table 18: Human Task Identification KPIs

KPIs	Number of actions identified	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Detection rate	False Alarm rate
DESCRIPTION		Accuracy = $(TP+TN) / GT$	Precision = $TP / (TP+FP)$	Recall = $TP / (TP+FN)$	DR = $TP / (TP+FN)$	FAR = $FP / (TP+FP)$
MEASURE UNIT	Number	%	%	%	%	%
BASELINE	>100	70%	70%	75%	75%	30%
TARGET (GOIZPER)	>15	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%
TARGET (NISSAN)	>15	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%
TARGET (ALSTOM)	>15	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%
TARGET (CEMBRE)	>15	80%	80%	80%	80%	20%

4.6 Module #6: Human Aware dynamic planning and scheduling for HRC Tasks

The general goal of the human aware dynamic planning and scheduling module (#6) is to develop a dynamic task planning system which is both human and context aware hence able to both reason on the user model and interpret a number of sensorial information by connection with other modules of the system (modules #1-5). In this regard, the task planning system is responsible for continuously creating and keep updated a collaborative plan for the robot adapted to the actual operative context.

Qualitative KPI concerning efficiency will be considered

- Reduction of robot idle time: This is to measure the reduction of idle time of robot (and a potential increase of its velocity) in performing collaborative tasks. The target is to provide a 20% reduction of idle time maximizing the effectiveness of robot operation.
- Improvement of productivity: This is to measure the increase of production capacity of a specific working cell. The task planning system will effectively distribute tasks among human and robot enhancing the production capability. A 20% reduction of production time is foreseen.
- Throughput increase: This is to measure the increase of throughput. The task planner will better coordinate human-robot collaborative tasks and better distribute tasks. The target is a 15% increase.

The decision values sub-module will use pieces of information saved in the Knowledge Base and data from the environment cognition system about the actual status of the system (the inputs) to derive decision values (the outputs) that will be used as triggers for the main planner. To represent this sub-module, the Accuracy KPI is therefore defined. The correctness of the decisions is determined by a human and, afterwards, the correct rates are computed as the ratio between the decision values that were correctly determined by the algorithm and the total number of decision values.

Table 19: Human Aware dynamic planning and scheduling for HRC Tasks KPIs

KPIs	Robot idle time	Improvement of productivity	Makespan	Accuracy
DESCRIPTION	Robot idle time	Improvement of the capacity to produce vs throughput	Production Process time	Correct vs total number of decision values
MEASURE UNIT	%	%	%	%
BASELINE	Robot idle time with no task planning	Productivity with no task planning	production time with no task planning	-
TARGET (GOIZPER)	-20%	+15%	-20%	75%
TARGET (NISSAN)	-20%	+15%	-20%	50%
TARGET (ALSTOM)	-20%	+15%	-20%	75%
TARGET (CEMBRE)	-20%	+15%	-20%	75%

4.7 Module #7: Offline and real-time human aware and safe robot motion planning

In module #7, the goal is the design of innovative methodologies for online and offline motion planning, dealing with complex application scenarios where human is a non-controllable resource.

Therefore, the KPIs of the module are related to the increase of easiness for the operator in using the robot, the increase of productivity for the working cell and the improvement of the ergonomics and acceptance of the robot by the human operator.

To test the solutions deployed in this project, a comparison with state-of-the-art practices will be conducted. In particular, the comparison is composed of:

- Benchmarking with state-of-the-art planners available in the Open Motion Planner Library³;
- Simulation tests on a mock-up scenario;
- Experimental tests on a mock-up scenario.

Specifically, the defined metrics to evaluate the success of the planning module are the following:

1. Improvement of the State of the art in motion planning in a complex industrial scenario:
 - a. Challenge: Reduction of 20% of the length of collision free trajectories in a shared workspace with a large number of obstacle
 - b. Baseline: benchmarking with state-of-the-art motion planners available in the Open Motion Planner Library [1] with a maximum computing time (4 seconds)
2. Improvement of the easiness in programming the robot cell, i.e., indirect cost reduction:
 - Challenge: Reduction of 80% for programming time.
 - Baseline: an industrial mock-up scenario will be set up as test case. An operator will be asked to program the robot by following industrial best practices (e.g., point-by-point programming). A set of at least ten different trajectories will be tested.
3. Improvement of work-cell productivity, i.e., direct cost reduction:
 - a. Challenge: reduction of 30% of the robot cycle time thanks to the reduction of robot safety stops/holds
 - b. Baseline: simulation of a Speed and Separation Monitoring application according to ISO 10218/b-TS15666; the robot will slow down or stop based on the presence of the operator in static safety zones. Industrial best practices will be followed [2][3]. Simulations include simplified modeling of the operator as an autonomous agent; this will allow for repetitive and fair comparisons between the algorithms. Experimental tests will also be conducted to validate the results.
4. Improvement of the human acceptance of the robots, i.e., human factors:
 - Challenge: Increase of the 25% the dependability evaluation from the user;
 - Baseline: experimental tests on a mock-up scenario. The mock-up will reproduce a Speed and Separation Monitoring application according to ISO 10218/b-TS15666; the robot will slow down or stop based on the presence of the operator in static safety zones. Industrial best practices will be followed^{4,5} A human factor analysis will be conducted by means of questionnaires to evaluate the dependability of the proposed solution compared to the baseline. At least 20 persons will participate in the tests. Dependability factors will be defined according to the literature⁶.

³ Ioan A. Şucan, Mark Moll, Lydia E. Kavraki, The Open Motion Planning Library, IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, 19(4):72–82, December 2012. <http://ompl.kavrakilab.org>

⁴ Jeremy A. Marvel, Rick Norcross, Implementing speed and separation monitoring in collaborative robot workcells, Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing, Volume 44, 2017, Pages 144-155

⁵ B. Matthias and T. Reisinger, "Example Application of ISO/TS 15066 to a Collaborative Assembly Scenario," *Proceedings of ISR 2016: 47st International Symposium on Robotics*, Munich, Germany, 2016, pp. 1-5.

⁶ Lasota, P. A., & Shah, J. A. (2015). Analyzing the Effects of Human-Aware Motion Planning on Close-Proximity Human–Robot Collaboration. *Human Factors*, 57(1), 21–33

Table 20: Offline and real-time human aware and safe robot motion planning KPIs

KPIs	Motion Planning	Easiness in programming the robot cell	Work-cell productivity	Human acceptance
DESCRIPTION	Length of collision free trajectories in a shared workspace	Programming time	Robot cycle time because of safety stops/holds	Increase the dependability evaluation from the user
MEASURE UNIT	%	%	%	%
BASELINE	OMPL motion planners ⁴ with maximum computing time	Manual programming in a mock-up scenario	Simulation of a Speed and Separation Monitoring application as per ISO 10218/b-TS15666 and best practices ^{5,6}	Experiments on a Speed and Separation Monitoring application as per ISO 10218/b-TS15666 and best practices ^{5,6}
TARGET (GOIZPER)	-20%	-80%	-30%	+25%
TARGET (NISSAN)	-20%	-80%	-30%	+25%
TARGET (ALSTOM)	-20%	-80%	-30%	+25%
TARGET (CEMBRE)	-20%	-80%	-30%	+25%

4.8 Module #8: Robot Motion Planning based on learning from demonstration

The Robot Motion Planning based on learning from demonstration module is responsible for building predictive motion models of humans, in order to ensure a safer and faster robot motion planner. The predicted trajectories can be used for the improvement of algorithm-based paths. For this model, deterministic and stochastic prediction accuracy metrics have been defined.

Module #8 is in charge of developing the human motion prediction modules. Long-term prediction is a hard task and, today, the most common approaches consider Linear Dynamics and Gaussian Distributions techniques. Module #8 objective is to integrate non-linear dynamics and non-gaussian distributions in order to do more accurate probabilistic predictions of the human motion.

Two possible KPI's have been defined to compare our results: the deterministic one, will compute the accuracy of the mean value of the generated trajectories, while the stochastic one will compute probability of a certain trajectory to belong to our predicted distribution. As the development for this module is still in progress, it is difficult, at this stage, to define specific expected improvements over the State of Art methods. Moreover, learning algorithms results are highly dependent on the amount, quality and type of the dataset used for training the models. Therefore, the estimating of specific targets for the defined metrics is currently not possible for any use case scenario and will be proposed and updated when all datasets will be available and will have been analysed.

Table 21: Robot Motion Planning based on learning from demonstration KPIs

KPIs	Prediction Accuracy (Deterministic)	Prediction Accuracy (Stochastic)
DESCRIPTION	Reduction in the error between the real human motion and the predicted motion	Maximize the probability of the future human motion to come from our model
MEASURE UNIT	mm	%
BASELINE	Linear Dynamic System	Linear Gaussian Models
TARGET (GOIZPER)	-	-
TARGET (NISSAN)	-	-
TARGET (ALSTOM)	-	-
TARGET (CEMBRE)	-	-

4.9 Module #9: Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication

This module is designed to provide smart solutions for enhancing the interaction of human operators with the rest Sharework’s system. Augmented reality application running on headset devices and smart screen applications for tablet are some of the designed approaches for publishing information to the workers. Considering that interfaces are heavily connected to the requirements and characteristics of each scenario, the features and functionalities of human-system interfaces are unique and vary between different activities. Moreover, the assessment of those interfaces is based on the impression and experiences of users meaning that state of the art cannot provide a solid performance baseline as reference. In the content of SHAREWORK project, it is believed that the most suitable approach to estimate metrics that evaluate the performance of interfaces is the implementation of surveys. Those surveys will be shared with the end-users in order each operator to express its opinion on the effectiveness of the interfaces and their performance in a series of indicators. The surveys will be performed anonymously, for ensuring integrity, and the operator will have to answer in the following types of questions:

- Single answer questions
- Multiple answer questions
- Rating scale questions (e.g. 1 to 10, poor performance to excellent performance, strongly agree to strongly disagree, etc.)
- Ranking questions

Table 22: Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication KPIs

KPIs	Easiness of use	Easiness of learning	Balancing of information	AR app confusing
DESCRIPTION	Ease of interface usage and interaction with the system	Ease of interface usage learning	Ease of identifying most relevant information	Frequency of app functionalities misunderstanding

MEASURE UNIT	rate 1-10	rate 1-10	rate 1-10	rate 1-10
TARGET (GOIZPER)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3
TARGET (NISSAN)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3
TARGET (ALSTOM)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3
TARGET (CEMBRE)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3

4.10 Module #10: Continuous evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction

The continuous and dynamic real-time assessment will need data inputs, provided by Module #2, Module #3 and Module #5 (e.g. manual material handling object information, joint positions, angles and semantic task information).

With the help of AWSlight, the original pre-SHAREWORK workplace can be compared to the new designed workplace (with the SHAREWORK modules implemented). The rough screening method AWSlight will provide a quick, initial assessment of manual activities at workstations in assembly areas or at workstations and provide an overview of possible stress centres.

The module will consist of two sub-modules and provides two main outputs:

Short Term (Online)-Evaluation and Feedback - During the execution of the work the worker gets feedback regarding his posture. Online feedback will be based primarily on posture analysis, as risk factors such as the number of repetitions and action forces are less suitable for consideration in an online feedback system. The influence of the latter factors depends strongly on the temporal domain.

Long-term Ergonomics (Shift) Report - Since most risk factors are assessed taking into account the time of exposure, it is appropriate to consider these factors in a long-term assessment. The core of this module is the use of the Ergonomic Assessment Work-Sheet (EAWS) method. Additional data collected via the short-term sub-module can also be optionally included.

The results of the ergonomic assessment should be proceeded in Module #9 to provide the worker real-time feedback on his current ergonomic behaviour and to guide him how to improve it.

Table 23: Continuous evaluation of Human ergonomics and posture correction KPIs

KPIs	Improved Ergonomics	Accuracy
DESCRIPTION	Improvement of worker ergonomics score (before and after module implementation)	Online Posture Feedback and Offline Ergonomics Score (Automated module vs. ergonomics expert)
MEASURE UNIT	AWSlight Screening (Score)	Interrater Reliability (Intra-class correlation coefficient, ICC)

BASELINE	AWS Light analysis result before Human ergonomics and posture correction	-
TARGET (GOIZPER)	ergonomic improvement to light grey rating (level 2 of 4)	ICC \geq 0,7
TARGET (NISSAN)	ergonomic improvement to light grey rating (level 2 of 4)	ICC \geq 0,7
TARGET (ALSTOM)	ergonomic improvement to light grey rating (level 2 of 4)	ICC \geq 0,7
TARGET (CEMBRE)	ergonomic improvement to light grey rating (level 2 of 4)	ICC \geq 0,7

4.11 Module #11: Human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative and high-payload robots

The relevant parameters for a safe collaboration are:

- System flexibility by dynamic zone-model, with respect to the Robot;
- Dynamic sensor management for redundant data processing with dynamic zones and level of interaction (HRC-level by IWU);
- Dynamic risk assessment with system stops while individual breaks security lines or danger zones;
- Safe computing architecture by using FPGA for deterministic Robot Real-time communication with period of 8ms.

The quality of this parameters will be measured with process KPIs, such as the increase of admissible robot speed and the overall process time reduction, in an economic way.

There currently is no metric that can be used as a baseline for these KPIs, because current methods can only compare initial situations and further solutions by using conventional safety sensors (e.g. Safety Integrity Level or Performance Level).

Table 24: Human safety in HRC tasks with collaborative and high-payload robots KPIs

KPIs	Increased Speed	Overall Process time reduced
DESCRIPTION	Overall permissible speed of Robot with Human in 3m range	Reduction in Robot idle time due to unnecessary stops from previous static safety zones
MEASURE UNIT	rate 1-10 (mm/s)	rate 1-10 (Robot Idle time in minutes vs Process time)
BASELINE	-	-
TARGET (GOIZPER)	> 3	> 5
TARGET (NISSAN)	> 2.5	> 3
TARGET (ALSTOM)	> 3	> 5
TARGET (CEMBRE)	> 2.5	> 3

4.12 Module #12: Tooling Sensors adaption for safe HRC

This module is concerned with adapting the safety system from 4.11 onto the local frame. Therefore, a sensor is mounted close to the local robotic structure, which evaluates the space surrounding the tool. Based on this the module sets triggers for the safety system that are evaluated in the dynamic risk analysis of 4.11.

The relevant parameters are:

- **Reaction Time:** The time it takes to detect an insertion into a safety restricted zone.
- **Speed Increase:** as 4.11
- **Overall Process Time Reduction:** as 4.11

Table 25: Tooling Sensors adaption for safe HRC KPIs

KPIs	Accuracy	Reliability	Computational efficiency
DESCRIPTION	Accuracy in detecting known (taught-in) items	The rate of relevant items in the environment that are segmented using the unsupervised segmentation in each scan	Overall processing time to process a full scan set
MEASURE UNIT	ms	rate 1-10 (mm/s)	rate 1-10 (Robot Idle time in minutes/Process)
BASELINE	Required by 4.11	No baseline	No baseline
TARGET (GOIZPER)	< 200ms	>3	>5
TARGET (NISSAN)	< 200ms	>2.5	>3
TARGET (ALSTOM)	< 200ms	>3	>5
TARGET (CEMBRE)	< 200ms	>2.5	>3

4.13 Module #13: Data security

The Data Security module will develop a specific security policy and prescribe policies for the communications and operations management, as well as access control policies to fortify the overall information security of the system. These policies will be the result of a dedicated and diligent analysis of the involved systems.

The aim of the aforementioned policies will be to mitigate the identified potential threats related to privacy, identity and integrity in order to provide an adequate level of security.

Effectively the developed data security module will be a toolset. This toolset will provide both data security Policies and Practices as well as a list of software libraries and tools that will aim to increase the data security of the software systems. The toolset will be generic and potentially

applicable to all use cases and modules. Use case developers and module developers will be able to select and apply tools and policies to fortify the data security where needed.

Usual Data security KPIs tend to quantify the security incidents and the effects of security incidents. Some common Data Security KPIs are provided below for completeness. Identifying, managing, recording and analyzing security incidents is paramount to enhancing data security.

- Number of Reported Incidents;
- Number of Major Security Incidents;
- Number of Small Security Incidents;
- Cost Per Incident;
- Amount of Time to Resolve an Incident;
- Downtime During an Incident.

In order to be applicable, these KPIs require installations that are open to data security incidents in real operating environments. This particular condition is not normally available during prototypes development and is not expected to be applicable during the project. Therefore, measuring the aforementioned data Security KPIs may not be practical or meaningful in the SHAREWORK project. Nevertheless, the consortium will aim to measure , to the extend possible, some of these KPIs for analysis and completeness.

However, a practical measure of the application of the policy would be to quantify the number of security standards, tools and policies implemented and available to use for each use case.

Table 26: Data Security KPIs

KPIs	Reported data security related incidents	Threats types foreseen	Data Security Safeguards
DESCRIPTION	The number of reported data security related incidents.	The number of potential data security threats that have been identified in the given environment and application.	The number of Data Security Safeguards included in data security policies, tools and policies that are used in order to prevent and nullify potential data security threats.
MEASURE UNIT	Number	Number	Number
BASELINE	No baseline for comparison considering that the baseline data security KPI's depend on the environment and external factors such as cyber-attacks. It can also depend on the application and human factors.		
TARGET (GOIZPER)	>3	>=3	>=3
TARGET (NISSAN)	>3	>=3	>=3
TARGET (ALSTOM)	>3	>=3	>=3
TARGET (CEMBRE)	>3	>=3	>=3

4.14 Module #14: Operator training through AR

In general, this module concerns the same aspects described for module 9 *Direct and natural human-system and system-human communication*. Therefore, the same major categories for the evaluation of the usability of the AR system have been identified and will be used for the evaluation of this module performances.

Regarding the operator training through AR specifically, two approaches are required to evaluate its performance: on the one hand the evaluation of the time required by an operator to adapt to changes in the task processes; on the other hand the evaluation of the time required to introduce the workflow to a new operator, in comparison with the same task without the cobot.

The evaluation of the gesture recognition algorithm, which will be implemented within this module, is closely linked with the human tracking in module #3.

Table 27: Operator training through AR KPIs

KPIs	Easiness of use	Easiness of learning	Balancing of information	AR app confusing	Training time reduction	Human error reduction
DESCRIPTION	Ease of interface usage and interaction with the system	Ease of interface usage learning	Ease of identifying most relevant information	Frequency of app functionalities misunderstanding	Time required for reading manuals and traditional training vs using AR app	Number of human errors during traditional training vs using AR app
MEASURE UNIT	rate 1-10	rate 1-10	rate 1-10	rate 1-10	%	%
BASELINE	No baseline for comparison considering that HMI's performance is related to the application and human factors					
TARGET (GOIZPER)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3	40%	80%
TARGET (NISSAN)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3	40%	80%
TARGET (ALSTOM)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3	40%	80%
TARGET (CEMBRE)	> 8	> 7	> 7	< 3	40%	80%

5 Conclusions

D1.7 moves from the basis of the work presented in D1.6 to present a comprehensive set of specific performance indicators for the industrial impact of the ShareWork system in the four project use case and for the evaluation of the twelve sharework modules performances.

For the industrial impact KPIs, the four ShareWork drivers have again been used as a reference basis to drive the metrics definition. Human-factors metrics, in particular, have been presented as an essential aspect of a successful implementation of collaborative robotic system in industrial applications and methodologies for both system evaluation and guidance in its development have been discussed.

For all four end users, specific KPIs have been defined and detailed, providing an insight on the specific tasks actions and tools to complete the information provided to the reader. These KPIs are representative of the end users' needs and requirements in terms of Productivity, Cost and Safety, and will measure the efficacy and efficiency of the ShareWork system in addressing specific industrial needs.

At a lower level, each single module of the ShareWork system has been addressed, providing insight on its objective, current state of the art methodologies to be reached or overcome and foreseen practices for the evaluation of its performances inside the ShareWork complete system. For each module a specific table of KPIs has been provided, comprehensive of target to be reached in the project and baseline to measure the starting point before ShareWork development and implementation.

The information collected in this deliverable will be essential in WP7, when the system validation campaign and performance assessment will be performed.